

Young Researchers Seminar 2023

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THE EFFECTS OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON MOBILITY

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SUMMARY

Now that the COVID-19 pandemic crisis is over, there is a lot of unanswered questions regarding what the “new normality” is going to look like. Evidence points to the fact that teleworking is going to be a part of it, however, up to this day there has been little information regarding the mid-term effects of teleworking on mobility because most studies were conducted while restrictions were still in place. At the same time, teleworking as a policy to reduce travel demand has been around for decades with limited success. To understand the effects and implications of working from home, this article will analyse mobile phone travel demand data before and after the pandemic in Catalunya. An econometric model is used to predict what the generated trips would have been if only socioeconomic factors are considered in both 2021 and 2022. The results show that the mean difference between the calculated trips and the real ones was -14% for 2021 and -11% for 2022. Additionally, data from national surveys states that the number of people who worked from home in 2021 increased by 13% in 2021 and 9% in 2022. The percentual gap between the real generated trips and the calculated matches the percentual increase in teleworking, which might indicate that the reason why trips are not fully reaching the predicted values is the working from home policy. The implications of this paper can guide policy-makers to understand the feasibility and implications of encouraging teleworking as a demand management solution in ever-increasing congested regions.

INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic that struck the world at the end of 2019 (Pase, Chiariotti, Zanella, & Zorzi, 2020) has fundamentally altered not only health and economies but also mobility worldwide, raising new challenges for transportation (Wang, et al., 2021). Towards the end of 2022 the situation began to stabilise and now a question arises: what does the “new normality” look like?

The Oxford COVID-19 Government Response Tracker (OxCGRT) provides a systematic way to track the stringency of government responses to COVID-19 across countries and time using a novel index (Stringency Index) that combines various measures of government responses. Nationwide lockdown measures came into force in Spain on 14 March 2020, two weeks after the start of the COVID-19 outbreak in the country. As one of the countries hardest hit by the virus, the mobility restrictions during the lockdown were among the strictest globally, reaching a value of 90 out of 100 in the Stringency Index by April 2020 (Hale, Petherick, Phillips, & Webster, 2020).

Mobility and transportation in Spain were highly affected, and it is to be determined if the situation will go back to how it was before the pandemic. The necessity for social distance had shaped mobility patterns long after the end of the lockdown, and its ripples might have long term, or even permanent, effects on urban planning and mobility (Pase, Chiariotti, Zanella, & Zorzi, 2020).

Working from home emerged as a growing trend in the post-pandemic era. Many companies used telework as an emergency solution, in order to be able to continue most non-essential productive activities, and we can now conceive future socio-occupational scenarios in which telework is more recurrent (Badia, et al., 2021).

In Spain during the lockdown 49,7% of the companies implemented temporary work from home policies and by the end of 2021 that value was at 45,5%. Before the confinement, the proportion of people who teleworked habitually was 4,8%. After the pandemic, in 2021 it stood at 17,6% and it decreased to 14% in 2022 (Cuerdo-Vilches, Navas-Martín, & Oteiza, 2021) (Instituto Nacional de Estadística, 2022).

This article aims to examine the mid-term effects of the working from home policies on mobility in Catalunya. This paper is structured as follows: the following section contains a state of the art with literature regarding mobility changes during the pandemic and the relationship with telecommuting and mobility reduction. The second section describes the methodology used to predict the generated trips in 2021 and 2022 based on socio-economic factors. The third presents some results and the fourth is a final discussion and conclusions.

1. STATE OF THE ART

There is already a body of literature regarding teleworking, the immediate pandemic's effect on mobility and the relationship between teleworking and the changes in mobility. However, there is no literature regarding the mid-term effects of teleworking on mobility after the pandemic since most studies were conducted during the lockdown or when restrictions were still in place.

1.1. TELEWORKING

Before the pandemic, there were already a few articles that studied teleworking and its possible implementation in modern society. Some authors proposed a framework in 1997 for estimating the telecommuting adoption process in the United States using a dynamic generalised ordinal probit model (Yen & Mahmassani, 1997), and some others studied telecommuting's potential in 2017 as a sustainable mobility tool in Canada in order to reduce overall travel time and peak hour travel, and to increase non-motorised travel 77% (Lachapelle, Tanguay, & Neumark-Gaudet, 2018).

Whenever the pandemic started, several articles were published analysing the new working-from-home arrangement. Questions were raised concerning the feasibility and future survival of telecommuting. "Is our housing ready?" was investigated by using online questionnaires in Spain. The results suggested that the adequacy of these spaces was insufficient for more than a quarter of the homes in the country (Cuerdo-Vilches, Navas-Martín, & Oteiza, 2021). The question "How many jobs can be performed at home?" was studied by classifying the feasibility of working from home for all occupations and merging this classification with occupational employment counts. It found that around 37% of the jobs in the US could be entirely performed at home, even if lower-income economies had a lower share of jobs that can be done at home (Dingel & Neiman, 2020).

Some studies analysed the behaviour of those workers who already worked from home compared to the ones that started with the pandemic (Reiffer, Magdolen, & Ecke, 2022), stating that some factors such as the household configuration had an influence on the choice of teleworking. For example, people with kids were more likely to work from home. This literature was conducted with data from before and during the pandemic, so it provided useful guidelines to understand the teleworking phenomenon but it did not contain information regarding the post-pandemic working situation.

Finally, there was some literature that studied the increase in teleworking during the pandemic, compared to what it used to be. Data from surveys before and during the COVID-19 pandemic

(June-October 2018 and March-April 2020) in the US was analysed. The conclusion was that there was a large shift from commuting to telecommuting, even if that shift was not consistent across income levels (Matson, McElroy, Lee, & Circella, 2022). The impact of COVID-19 on telecommuting and travel during the first year of the pandemic in the US was studied with a particular focus on examining the variation in impact across different geographies. It was observed that nearly one-third of the workforce worked from home during the pandemic, which was six times higher than the pre-pandemic period (Rafiq, McNally, & Uddin, 2022).

1.2. MOBILITY DURING THE PANDEMIC

Whenever the pandemic started, a dramatic change in mobility patterns occurred in the major cities around the world, resulting in a considerable amount of literature analysing this phenomenon. The vast majority of the literature had an environmental approach, studying how a reduction in mobility had a positive effect on air pollution and Greenhouse Gas emissions (Peters, 2021) (Rahman, Paul, & Hossain, 2021). Findings in a case study of a Mediterranean city showed that the mean CO_2 levels were not significantly affected during lockdown period, while the mean NO_2 levels decreased by 32% (Sifakis, Aryblia, Daras, & Tournaki, 2021). Regarding the effects on transportation, most literature focused on describing the pandemic situation and predicted possible outcomes, but there is none describing the mid-term changes introduced in mobility.

Some researches focused in describing the reduction in trips during the lockdown by analysing smartphone data provided by sources such as Facebook, Google, Citymapper or GPS. A study analysed the impact of non-pharmaceutical countermeasures in 41 cities worldwide in March 2020, observing how mobility declined in all of them (Vannoni, McKee, Semenza, Bonell, & Stuckler, 2020). A relationship was observed between the mobility restrictions, the COVID-19 waves and the decrease in travel, and tracking mobility during the pandemic was an effective tool to help guide the restriction policies (Pérez-Arnal, et al., 2021). In the US, it was observed that an official stay-at-home restriction order corresponded to reducing mobility by 7,9% (Engle, Stromme, & Zhou, 2020). A special case occurred in Japan, where restrictions were not enforced, but highly recommended by the government. It was found that mobility reductions answered to the declarations of emergency by examining the temporal trend in March 2020 with data from Yahoo Japan (Nomura, et al., 2021).

There were some particular case studies in major cities such as NYC, Barcelona or Budapest (Wang, et al., 2021) (Peters, 2021) (Bucsky, 2020), where the change in mobility patterns was analysed. The techniques in that literature included calibrating simulation models with pandemic data, conducting surveys and studying data from different modes of transport. All these articles had a purpose of analysing the big picture in the chosen city by assessing the

overall travel reduction and changes in modal share and then helping policy-makers trace a plan for re-opening strategies.

Some articles focused on a specific transportation mode and how it had responded to the pandemic and the lockdown. The most drastic decrease in demand was seen in shared transportation modes, especially public transit (Mashrur, Lavoie, Wang, Loa, & Habib, 2022). Moreover, the public perception of transit had become increasingly negative as concerns over hygiene and other pandemic related factors grew, resulting in enormous greener mobility such as walking or cycling (Pase, Chiariotti, Zanella, & Zorzi, 2020) and placing more priority on pandemic related factors when choosing a mode (Abdullah, Dias, Muley, & Shahin, 2020). In New York, the bicycle modal share increased from 4,7% in March 2020 to 8,1% in June 2020, almost doubling its usage. In Budapest the bicycle usage also saw the greatest increase growth rate by more than doubling its share (Bucsky, 2020).

Driving behaviour and safety indicators were analysed in Greece and Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (KSA). There was an increase in speeds by 6-11% and a 12% increase of harsh accelerations and harsh breaking events, but there was a 41% reduction in accidents in the studied countries. The status of traffic safety and the public perception on traffic safety during the pandemic was studied, with results showing that the total numbers of car crashes in Qatar significantly reduced during the pandemic compared with the previous 5 years (Alhajyaseen, et al., 2022). Regarding the general public perceptions, more than 80% reported that roads became safer while driving behaviours improved during the pandemic. On the other hand, more than 50% of the experts disagreed that roads became safer, 55% disagreed that driving behaviours improved and 70% agreed that less attention from governments was directed toward road safety during the pandemic.

1.3. TELEWORKING EFFECTS ON MOBILITY

There has been some literature defining the factors that affected the reduction in mobility during and immediately after the pandemic, and studies have analysed the potential influence working from home might have had. Changes in mobility in the US in early pandemic stages were studied in order to provide an analytical framework and explore the contributing factors (Chakraborty, Mahmud, & Gates, 2022) (Hoseinzadeh, Gu, & Zhang, 2021). The results indicated that the factors significantly influencing daily trips included the percentage of people working from home, combined with other socioeconomic factors. Other studies included surveys studying the main purpose of travel, showing how it had shifted from work to shopping, suggesting that teleworking had made people stop travelling for work (Abdullah, Dias, Muley, & Shahin, 2020). Finally, a case study of the MIT campus community was presented, using data from a pre-pandemic transportation survey as well as data on the academic groups and home locations of the broader population (Berke, Doorley, & Alfonso, 2022). These data were

used to estimate car commuter miles and to model and evaluate interventions in relation to reducing car commuter miles. There was an estimated 16% reduction in car commuter miles if staff worked from home 1 day a week.

Other studies started to think ahead and tried to predict to what extent teleworking was here to stay and what would happen to mobility if that was true. An expert survey was conducted asking about the long-term changes with the pandemic (Zhang, Hayashi, & Frank, 2021). The results showed that 77,8% of the experts agreed that “working from home will become popular” and 34,2% expected that more and more people would choose a job that allowed them to mainly work from home. Changes in teleworking during the lockdown in April 2020 and the intention to change commuting behaviour after COVID-19 was examined in a case study in the Netherlands (Kalter, Geurs, & Wismans, 2021). The results suggested that employees with a relatively large change in teleworking during the early lockdown expected to work from home more frequently after COVID-19, and that car use was expected to decrease after COVID-19, mostly because of an increase in teleworking.

In conclusion, the pandemic has probably shaped mobility in an unprecedented way by not only reducing its numbers but also affecting travel purposes and modal choices. And it can be reasoned that teleworking has played a part in it. However, there needs to be further research in the mid and long-term effects regarding the relationship between working from home and changes in mobility.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study aims to analyse the relationship between teleworking and the change in mobility in Catalunya from before to after the pandemic. The structure of the methodology is as follows in Figure 1. Available data on mobility and socio-economic variables from before the pandemic has been studied, and trips generated in 2020 have been used altogether with socio-economic factors in order to build an econometric model that predicts the generated trips in 2021 and 2022 from the variables. These predicted trips have been compared with the actual number of trips for both 2021 and 2022. The aim of this calculation is to assess if the loss in mobility trips is related to socio-economic factors or if it is due to another phenomenon.

Figure 1: structure of the methodology

2.1. VARIABLES USED FOR TRIP GENERATION

Mobility data has been obtained from origin-destination mobile phone data from Ministry of Transports, Mobility and Urban Agenda (Ministerio de Transportes, 2022).

The trip generation stage of the classical transport model aims at predicting the total number of trips generated in each zone of the study area (Ortúzar & Willumsen, 2011). This can be achieved either with the trips of the individuals who reside in each zone or directly with some properties of the zones. The following factors have been found relevant affecting trip generation in practical studies: income, car ownership, family size, household structure, value of land, residential density, accessibility, zonal employment and number of employees. This study used the zonal-based multiple regression, which aims to find a relationship between the number of trips produced by zone and average socio-economic characteristics of the households in each

zone (Ortúzar & Willumsen, 2011). The socio-economic variables considered in this study are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: variables used

Variable	Abbreviation
Gross Domestic Product per person	GDP
Affiliations to Social Security	ASS
Unemployment	U
University Students	US
Non-university Students	NUS
Vehicles	V
Agriculture	A
Industry	I
Construction	C
Services	S

2.2. ZONAL AGGREGATION

To homogenise different datasets, the study used aggregated zonal data. Catalunya is so heterogeneous in terms of socioeconomic characteristics that it is impossible to calibrate a regression that works for the whole region. Instead, some particular area had to be chosen for the study. Catalunya has three zonal levels: municipalities, counties and provinces. Socio-economic characteristics will be analysed first at the province level. It can be seen in Figure 2 that the province of Barcelona has a population of 5,7 million out of 7,7 million, which represents around 74% of the total. Also, it has a working population of 2,3 million out of 2,9 million, which is 77% out of the total. Therefore, the most representative area will be the province of Barcelona.

Figure 2: population in Catalunya

Once the area is selected, the level of aggregation has to be still determined. The Barcelona province contains 311 municipalities and 12 counties. These municipalities are not homogeneous and their characteristics vary too much to use a linear regression to calibrate all of them. As a result, the county level will be used, and the selected counties and their socio-economic characteristics are shown in Table 2 and Table 3.

Table 2: selected counties and their socio-economic characteristics (1)

County	GDP	ASS	U	US	NUS
Alt Penedès	28,1	46103	6160	2315	20015
Anoia	20,6	49516	8493	2330	21945
Bages	24,3	70554	11187	3785	30050
Baix Llobregat	29,3	351137	46571	18345	142190
Barcelonès	36,2	924173	132130	54025	311400
Berguedà	22,8	15242	2089	755	5620
Garraf	17,8	60223	9842	3045	23570
Maresme	19,7	182890	28605	10815	77130
Moianès	20,3	6181	610	345	2235
Osona	29	71013	8781	3875	28000
Vallès Occidental	29	391489	57976	23035	168970
Vallès Oriental	29,5	176802	25109	9350	73710

Table 3: selected counties and their socio-economic characteristics (2)

County	V	A	I	C	S
Alt Penedès	93273	120	11200	1570	19940
Anoia	100344	100	8070	1725	16040

Bages	215634	290	15605	2910	36520
Baix Llobregat	546798	170	48775	17715	205605
Barcelonès	1229792	265	81430	36230	976685
Berguedà	36666	135	1770	585	4995
Garraf	105007	15	3600	1680	17510
Maresme	320425	150	14840	5470	76525
Moianès	11927	60	1350	110	1240
Osona	132087	1075	19910	2320	32825
Vallès Occidental	634795	220	72955	16605	232070
Vallès Oriental	311152	250	38225	6770	69910

2.3. STUDY PERIODS

Finally, the study periods need to be determined. The Ministry provides three datasets that will be considered in this study:

1. From 17 February 2020 to 12 March 2020.
2. From 1 January 2021 to 9 May 2021.
3. From 1 April 2022 to 31 December 2022.

However, not all data could be considered in the study. Firstly, this study is analysing the possible effects of working from home, so only weekdays were considered. In order to assess if Fridays were worth considering, Figure 3 was plotted with trip data for every single day for February 2021 for the selected counties. It can be observed that Fridays have a different behaviour than the rest of the weekdays, so they have been considered part of the weekend and therefore, excluded from the study.

Figure 3: data for February 2021

February is a month that does not have any holiday in Spain, so holiday behaviour could not be observed. In order to do so, Figure 4 was plotted with trip data for the month of April 2021, where the 2nd and 5th were holidays. It can be seen that these days have a significantly lower number of trips than the rest of the weekdays, so holidays have been excluded from the study.

Figure 4: data for April 2021

Seasonal events needed to be analysed next. Figure 5 and Figure 6 plot the available data for 2021 and 2022 respectively, with weekends, Fridays and holidays already removed. For 2021

the number of trips is stable throughout the months, so no seasonal events take place. On the other hand, it is clear that 2022 presents a seasonal event in August. This is the month were most of the population in Spain uses paid vacation days. Therefore, the month of August has been excluded from the study.

Figure 5: data for 2021

Figure 6: data for 2022

3. RESULTS

This section will contain the values and conclusions obtained from the methodology already presented. The first section will include a pre-processing part, where the data is treated and cleaned. Then, the results from the econometric model will be analysed and finally the connection between those results and teleworking will be discussed.

3.1. PRE-PROCESSING

The explanatory variables required some pre-processing before being used in the model. In order to be significant, most of the variables needed to be in reference to each county. The way of doing so is shown in Equation 1. Considering a county i , the Affiliations to Social Security for that county ASS_i are divided by the population in the county P_i .

$$ASS/P = \frac{ASS_i}{P_i} \tag{1}$$

The Gross Domestic Product per person is the only variable that does not need any modification because it is already “per person”.

Variable	Abbreviation	After pre-processing
Gross Domestic Product per person	GDP	GDP
Affiliations to Social Security	ASS	ASS/P
Unemployment	U	U/P
University Students	US	US/P
Non-university Students	NUS	NUS/P
Vehicles	V	V/P
Agriculture	A	A/P
Industry	I	I/P
Construction	C	C/P
Services	S	S/P

3.2. CONSTRUCTION OF THE ECONOMETRIC MODEL

To build the model, the first step was to select the significant independent variables. The significant variables were the following:

- Unemployment (U/P)
- Industry (I/P)

- Services (S/P)

Let Y be a random variable and x a controllable variable, that is, the values x takes are set by the experimenter. It is assumed that Y is calculated for different values of x according to the following linear model. Therefore, the linear model correlates random response variable Y (endogenous variable) and a group of k non-random explanatory or regressive variables x_1, \dots, x_n (exogenous variables).

Let y_1, \dots, y_n be n independent observations of Y , the linear model of the multiple regression is defined as Equation 2.

$$y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_{i1} + \beta_2 x_{i2} + \beta_3 x_{i3} + \dots + \beta_k x_{ik} + \epsilon_i \quad (2)$$

In the present case, $k = 3$ because there is 3 explanatory variables, $i = 12$ because there are 12 counties, y is the number of predicted trips for every county and x are the socio-economic variables.

The resulting model is shown in Table 4.

Table 4: model results

Coefficients	Estimate	Standard Error	T value	P(> t)
Constant	2,7813	0,046	60,592	0,000
Unemployment/PC	0,1412	0,050	2,841	0,022
Industry/PC	0,1462	0,050	2,910	0,020
Services/PC	0,2568	0,046	5,526	0,001
R-squared	0,833	Adjusted R-squared	0,792	
F-statistic	13,31	P(F-statistic)	0,00178	

The coefficients show that the three variables are positively correlated to the dependent variable, because all estimates are positive. The most relevant one, with the highest estimate value, is the number of persons that works in the services sector. This could be explained by the fact that it is the sector that has more flexibility to work from home.

All the p-values of the model are significant at the 5%. The F-statistic test is less than alpha so the null hypothesis could not be rejected, thus the model is statistically significant. The model hypotheses were tested. The multicollinearity was tested with the VIF test with results shown in Table 5 and, since all values were smaller than 5, it could be concluded that there was no issue. The Ramsay Reset test had an F value of 2,89 and a p value of 0,13, so the null hypothesis that the model is correctly specified could not be rejected.

Table 5: VIF results

Feature	VIF
Unemployment/PC	1,173
Industry/PC	1,187
Services/PC	1,025

The residuals hypotheses were tested next. The Jarque Bera test had a value of 0,07 and a p value of 0,997, which indicated that the null hypothesis could not be rejected and therefore the residuals followed a normal distribution. The Breusch-Pagan test had an F value of 0,30 and a p value of 0,82, so the null hypothesis that homoscedasticity is present could not be rejected. Finally, the Durbin-Watson test had a value of 2,147 which indicated no correlation between instances.

3.3. TRIP GENERATION

The coefficients given by the model were the following:

$$\beta_0 = 2,7813$$

$$\beta_1 = 0,1412$$

$$\beta_2 = 0,1462$$

$$\beta_3 = 0,2568$$

The estimated trips for 2021 and 2022 were calculated by inserting the coefficients and the dependent variables related to 2021 and 2022 into Equation 1, respectively. The results are shown in Figure 7 and Table 6 for 2021 and in Figure 8 and Table 7 for 2022.

Figure 7: model results and generated trips for 2021

Table 6: model results and generated trips for 2021

County	County Code	Real Trips 2021	Calculated Trips 2021
Alt Penedès	3	299670	312514
Anoia	6	305175	352433
Bages	8	429119	539877
Baix Llobregat	12	2011939	2344388
Barcelonès	14	5705324	7526071
Berguedà	15	84537	93979
Garraf	18	370474	375312
Maresme	22	1083642	1191743
Moianès	23	27651	32364
Osona	26	421762	479178
Vallès Occidental	41	2485554	2858894
Vallès Oriental	42	1093454	1190811

Figure 8: model results and generated trips for 2022

Table 7: model results and generated trips for 2022

County	County Code	Real Trips 2022	Calculated Trips 2022
Alt Penedès	3	366029	315017
Anoia	6	345213	359717
Bages	8	479453	549853
Baix Llobregat	12	2250884	2328721
Barcelonès	14	7364917	7290162
Berguedà	15	81498	96147
Garraf	18	460821	377659
Maresme	22	1285869	1184579
Moianès	23	13566	32420
Osona	26	458463	487649
Vallès Occidental	41	3121753	2876396
Vallès Oriental	42	1103052	1192516

3.4. COMPARISON BETWEEN GENERATED RESULTS

In order to check if the results are coherent, two sets of data were compared for both 2021 and 2022:

- The percentual difference between the calculated trips and the generated trips.
- The percentual difference between the generated trips in 2020 and the year of study.

The difference between those percentages has been calculated in absolute value in order to see if they were of similar magnitude. The percentages will be considered of the same magnitude if the difference between them does not exceed 10%. Results for 2021 are shown in Table 8 and it can be observed that these percentages are of the same magnitude in all cases but two: Alt Penedès and Bages. Results for 2022 are in Table 9 and show that all percentages are of the same magnitude but three: Alt Penedès, Bages and Moianès.

Finally, the means of the values for all the counties are calculated, showing that the mean percentual difference between calculated and generated trips for 2021 is -14% and the mean percentual difference between generated trips in 2020 and 2021 is -13%. For 2022, the mean percentual difference between calculated and generated trips is -11% and the mean percentual difference between generated trips in 2020 and 2022 is -8%. Therefore, the difference in absolute value is 1% for 2021 and 3% in 2022.

Table 8: comparison for 2021

County	Percentual difference between calculated and generated trips (%)	Percentual difference between generated trips in 2020 and 2021 (%)	Difference in absolute value (%)
Alt Penedès	-4	-14	10
Anoia	-15	-10	5
Bages	-26	-13	13
Baix Llobregat	-16	-22	6
Barcelonès	-32	-30	2
Berguedà	-11	-7	4
Garraf	-1	-6	5
Maresme	-10	-8	2
Moianès	-17	-8	9
Osona	-14	-16	2
Vallès Occidental	-15	-16	1
Vallès Oriental	-9	-9	0
Mean	-14	-13	1

Table 9: comparison for 2022

County	Percentual difference between calculated and generated trips (%)	Percentual difference between generated trips in 2020 and 2022 (%)	Difference in absolute value (%)
Alt Penedès	14	-6	20
Anoia	-4	-3	1
Bages	-14	-1	13

Baix Llobregat	6	1	5
Barcelonès	-2	-5	3
Berguedà	-14	-7	7
Garraf	19	16	3
Maresme	9	10	1
Moianès	-143	-124	19
Osona	-7	-6	1
Vallès Occidental	8	8	0
Vallès Oriental	0	0	0
Mean	-11	-8	3

4. CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this study was to analyse the mid-term effects of teleworking on mobility because most existing studies were conducted while restrictions were still in place. In order to do so, this article presented an econometric model to predict what the generated trips in each county would have been if only socio-economic factors were considered.

The results are displayed in the form of the values of the percentual differences between the calculated and real trips for every county. Then, the mean of these values has been computed. In 2021 the mean difference was -14% and in 2022 it was -11%. Additionally, data from national surveys (Instituto Nacional de Estadística, 2022) states that the number of people who worked from home in 2021 increased by 13% in 2021 and 9% in 2022.

The conclusions drawn from the results of this paper point towards two facts. First, there is a bias between the results calculated from the econometric model and the real results, which might lead to think that the variation in the number of generated trips does not only depend on socio-economic factors. Second, the percentual gap between the real generated trips and the calculated matches the percentual increase in teleworking, which might indicate that the reason why trips are not fully reaching the predicted values is the working from home policy. However, the study does not present enough information in order to affirm that teleworking is the only reason that mobility has changed its values.

The implications of this paper can guide policy-makers to understand the feasibility and implications of encouraging teleworking as a demand management solution in ever-increasing congested regions.

5. REFERENCES

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